

Acetylation of some organic compounds under microwave irradiation

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Abstract : Acetic acid has been used for acetylation of seven aromatic amines and two phenols under microwave exposure. The time taken for these reactions ranges from 18–25 min with reasonably good yields (65–77%).

Keywords : Acetylation, microwave irradiation.

Acetylation is an important transformation in organic synthesis. A number of methods are available to carry out this reaction¹. The present work describes microwave-induced synthesis of anilides and acetates from some substituted amines and phenols using glacial acetic acid in the absence of zinc dust.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on a TECH-NU melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. All reactions were carried out in a commercially available domestic microwave oven (Kenstar Model No. OM 26 EGO) having a maximum power output of 1200 W operating at

2450 MHz. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR). Elemental analysis was carried out on Elementor Vario EL III Carbo Erba 1108.

A solution of substrate (0.054 mol) in glacial acetic acid (10.0 mL) was taken in a 100.0 mL Erlenmeyer flask fitted with a funnel as a loose top. The reaction mixture was then irradiated under microwave (40% power) for 30 s. After that, an interval of 15 s was allowed to avoid excessive evaporation of the solvent. This protocol was repeated for an appropriate time (as monitored by TLC). It was then cooled and the resulting solution was poured in ice-cold water. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from alcohol.

Table 1. Microwave induced acetylation using glacial acetic acid in solvent free condition (power = 40%)

Sl. no.	Substrate	Product	Reaction time (min)	Yield (%)
1.	2-Nitroaniline	2-Nitroacetanilide	25	72
2.	3-Nitroaniline	3-Nitroacetanilide	25	77
3.	2,4-Dinitroaniline	2,4-Dinitroacetanilide	20	72
4.	4-Chloroaniline	4-Chloroacetanilide	20	77
5.	4-Bromoaniline	4-Bromoacetanilide	20	73
6.	2-Naphthylamine	2-Naphthylacetanilide	18	72
7.	3-Methoxyaniline	3-Methoxyacetanilide	18	69
8.	2-Nitrophenol	2-Nitrophenylacetate	22	65
9.	3-Nitrophenol	3-Nitrophenylacetate	20	73

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